

THE INFLUENCE OF SOIL FERTILITY ON SOIL FERTILITY FROM LEGUMES

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Аннотация: в статье показано влияние на плодородие почвы бобовых, как повторного засева. При посеве бобовых в хлопковые поля и поля других культур они обогащают почву органическими веществами и создают дополнительную базу питательных веществ. Бобовые не только обогащают почву и являются кормом для скота, но и выполняют фитосанитарные задачи, очищая почву от вредителей и болезней.

Ключевые слова: Дурдона, Хилола, Коралл, Турон, прекрасно, определённо виды нута, минерал, монокультура

Abstract: The article repeats legumes crop as Effect of sown bean varieties on soil fertility The soil is organic when crops are planted in cotton and other crops enriched with substances and creates an additional base of ozone. Bean grain crops only feed on livestock, increasing soil fertility substance is not only a means of producing, but is also harmful phytosanitary to remove insect and disease infections It also functions.

Keywords: Durдона, Khilola, Coral, Turon, Fine, Certain types of mash, mineral, monoculture.

Currently, about 46 percent of the total irrigated lands in our country are of varying degrees of salinity, of which 18 percent are strongly and moderately saline, and more than 23 percent are classified as low quality lands. Most of the lands with unsatisfactory state of reclamation belong to the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Syrdarya and Fergana regions. Leguminous crops are of great importance in increasing the productivity of these lands, and their cultivation at different depths has a positive effect on soil fertility.

For this purpose, it is necessary to constantly increase the soil fertility and use all internal possibilities of agricultural development wisely.

When leguminous crops are planted in cotton fields, they affect the process of always planting the same crop in the same field (monoculture), creating a unique short-term crop rotation system. These crops occupy the cotton fields from the time the cotton is harvested until it is replanted next year.

Legumes, when planted in the field of cotton and other crops, enrich the soil with organic matter and create a unique base. Because leguminous grain crops leave 3-4 tons and more organic matter on each hectare of land during autumn, winter and spring. At the same time, it gives an opportunity to get 100-150 quintals and more from each hectare of land, confined to the land for livestock, in the period of scarcity.

Leguminous grain crops are not only a means of increasing soil fertility and growing feed for livestock, but also perform a phytosanitary function, cleaning from infections of various

harmful insects and diseases. Planting, harvesting, fertilizing, watering and other agrotechnical measures of leguminous crops protect the land from various natural disasters in autumn, winter, and spring, and ensure the improvement of the soil. When cotton is grown on such lands, its productivity increases. [1]

Another positive effect of legumes on agrotechnical measures in cotton fields is the vitality of their root system. Mung beans (or other types of beans) are planted in wide rows in late April or May, as a repeat crop in late June. The row spacing is 60 cm, the planting system is 60x20, 60x15. Sowing 0.25-0.40 million seeds are planted at the rate of 10 kg/ha. Mung beans are planted in grain drills, and common beans are planted in corn or seed drills. The planting depth is 3-5 cm, it is watered 3-5 times during the growing season, and the rows are mulched. It is watered more during the period of flowering and fruiting. If mash is planted for blue manure, when the grain is finished, the roller is pressed, then it is disced on both sides and it is plowed at a depth of 27-30 cm using a small plow [2]. Herbicides used in legumes against weeds are also recommended to be used in beans.

In Uzbekistan, the types of mosh that grow in the ground are widespread, the weight of 1000 of their seeds is 40-80 grams. Issyksevar said that although this plant germinates in 5-7 days at a temperature of 12-15 degrees, most jaidari mosh species require a lot of water, especially during the cultivation, they do not develop well in shady areas, and the grains remain small. I can't help but admit it. In addition, considering that mash is one of the products suitable for export, it is not difficult to understand which countries can become our direct customers.

Because, as an example, Afghanistan, India, Iran and other Asian countries alone have the opportunity to grow only 40% of this product compared to the demand for their population, so they buy 60% of it as imports. At present, you can see that this legume crop is cultivated on a large scale in the regions of Kashkadarya, Tashkent, Fergana, Andijan and Karakalpakstan. Cultivation of mash product not only as feed, but also as seed is very profitable.

The above-mentioned mash varieties are attracting interest from many people as they bring significant income as a second crop and enrich the land with minerals. In fact, crops such as mash, winter rapeseed and rye, peas, mustard, radish with perco oil, which are now widespread and are grown on almost all farms, have become the basis of feed for livestock. Therefore, paying attention to the planting of leguminous crops in many districts of our republic serves as a source of food for livestock and improving the condition of the soil.

References:

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